

Hidden Landscapes of Mediterranean Europe

Cultural and methodological biases in
pre- and protohistoric landscape studies

Proceedings of the international meeting
Siena, Italy, May 25-27, 2007

Edited by

Martijn van Leusen
Giovanna Pizziolo
Lucia Sarti

BAR International Series 2320
2011

Published by

Archaeopress
Publishers of British Archaeological Reports
Gordon House
276 Banbury Road
Oxford OX2 7ED
England
bar@archaeopress.com
www.archaeopress.com

BAR S2320

Hidden Landscapes of Mediterranean Europe: Cultural and methodological biases in pre- and protohistoric landscape studies. Proceedings of the international meeting Siena, Italy, May 25-27, 2007

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ISBN 978 1 4073 0903 3

Page layout by Metra - servizi per l'archeologia (Sesto Fiorentino, Italy)

Printed in England by 4edge, Hockley

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19 Two hidden landscapes in central Portugal: Rego da Murta (Alvaiázere) and Ocreza (Mação)

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Abstract

Since the 1990s, the TEMPOAR programme team has been developing several research projects on the prehistoric settlement of Alto Ribatejo (central Portugal). These interdisciplinary studies have contributed to a better understanding of the life and interrelationships of these populations. Based upon two ‘hidden landscapes’ located along the northern edge and in the south-east of the region (Rego da Murta in Alvaiázere and Ocreza in Mação), we will present the main conclusions reached so far, focusing on the range of options and behaviours of prehistoric populations that led us to a new approach and to go beyond the hidden-open dichotomy.

1. Introduction

Since Christopher Tilley (1994) published his phenomenological approach, a concern with the landscape problematic has been growing within the archaeological community. Tilley’s approach, however, is not the only possible one: others including Thomas (1993, 1996), Bradley (1998) and Ingold (2000) have also offered reflections. These approaches also had an impact on the development of spatial analyses employing Geographic Information Systems (e.g. Llobera 1996, 2001). This theoretical shift towards a phenomenological approach (despite the huge differences between Tilley’s, Ingold’s and Thomas’s works: see Ingold 2005) gave rise to the perception of landscape not as a determinative element (as according to an environmental determinism), but as an element interpreted according to the concept of *being in the world*. This shift has put the emphasis on the sensory aspect as an approach to understanding: concepts such as visibility, soundscapes and others have grown in importance. Actually, the topic of landscape visibility is a recent concern (see, for instance, the dedicated issue 39.1 of the World Archaeology journal, published in 2007).

So, what can we theoretically understand? Can we establish an understanding about what a ‘hidden landscape’ is or was? The introduction to the call for papers referred to the apparent diversity within the archaeological record of the Mediterranean region. It suggested that coastal sites were reasonably tracked, whereas mountain and valley sites were poorly recorded. This raises a methodological problem: are there more archaeological sites in coastal areas? Are these more visible than those in inland areas? Or are inland areas insufficiently studied?

Now, this characterization of mountain and valley landscapes as closed landscapes refers us again to issues such as landscape understanding, interpreta-

tion of its morphological characteristics and its relationship with the type of sites found therein. We do not want, however, to fall back into the fallacy of environmental determinism which dominated archaeology before, and even less to define cultural circles (which contain fallacies that are already identified and do not fall within the scope of this small paper).

When we consider the Portuguese case, and particularly the Alto Ribatejo region (inner central region of Portugal), it becomes clear that the idea of a hidden landscape is much more related to the presence of gaps in the archaeological record than to any access or visibility constraints of the archaeological record itself (in the sense that some regions have attributes that would make archaeological sites more visible than others). Inescapably, the work developed by our team in the Alto Ribatejo, particularly that of the current authors (Oosterbeek 1994; Figueiredo 2006) and Ana Rosa Cruz (1997), has attempted to fill pre-existing research gaps allowing the construction of a *visible* record rather than a *hidden* one as in Heidegger’s *Hervorbringen* approach.

The path proposed here is closely related to the hermeneutic approach to landscape perception, not only using modern visualisation tools such as GIS, but also the experience acquired during the process. Thus, in the study region two cases are worth mentioning as interesting examples of possible hidden landscapes. The first is the significant number of cave burials and initial unawareness of other practices in artificial monuments in the Nabão region. This made us realise that in limestone areas the type of occupation found in prehistoric burials would be different from that of neighbouring geological regions, when we compare these practices with invisible areas of limited access within closed landscapes or in more restricted social circles. The second case includes technical means in understanding all these

Figure 1 – Location of the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta in the northern part of the Alto Ribatejo region. To the east lies the Zêzere river.

different factors, where using more complex methodologies is necessary for a more reliable approach to the analysis of the archaeological record. This is the case with the prehistoric art of Ocreza Valley, which is mainly located in steep areas or on the banks of the Ocreza river and dispersed throughout its typical closed, mountain-fringed valley, which contributes to a greater invisibility. Despite the differences between them, these two examples help us explain how this *hidden-open* dichotomy can be overcome through systematic fieldwork.

2. Caves and megalithic monuments of the Nabão region

Until the last decade, the Nabão region was interpreted according to different patterns from those of neighbouring regions and practices in use in the Tagus or Zêzere regions. The structure, cults, materials and types of monuments characterised it as a unique region with its own characteristics, probably related with different social groups or different relationships/contacts, producing over time a unique, almost invisible archaeological case.

Therefore, studies developed in the nineties (Oosterbeek 1994; Cruz 1997) reflected an approach in which the Alto Ribatejo was split into two different areas: the Nabão linked to the cave world and originating from the cardial and the Tagus and Zêzere linked to the constructors of the megalithic monuments.

The earliest papers on cave contexts, such as that at Cadaval (Oosterbeek 1985), recognised contacts with the ‘megalithic world’, but still suggested on the basis of the archaeological record that the organization of the first Neolithic landscape in the Nabão region followed different rules from those found in the South. For example, in the Nabão region cave depositions were used instead of artificial monuments or nuclei standing out from the landscape as in the Tagus and Zêzere regions. Ritual features combined with artificial structures in cavities funnelling the entrances, the lack of data for bone deposition comparison, differences between the exhumed artefacts and those recorded in known megalithic monuments and the invisibility of these sites could be sufficient reasons for this region to be considered as a hidden landscape in the living sense of a prehistoric community that was different from the remainder.

A more systematic interpretation of parallel articulated rituals between the caves and the megaliths in the Later Neolithic was proposed in the mid-1990s (Oosterbeek 1995). However, the discovery (by father Jacinto from Pussos) of two megalithic monuments in the complex of Rego da Murta (including at least 3 dolmens and 7 menhirs located near the caves; see fig. 1) and further studies of the Tagus and Zêzere regions allowed the formulation of new theoretical models (Figueiredo 2005; 2007; in press). The data obtained enabled these researchers to establish

connections between both regions and the different types of monuments from at least the middle Neolithic onward, and to start viewing this region as a dominant element of a broader society incorporated in a broad contact network and possessing diverse internal ritual practices. It was no longer viewed as the result of hidden landscapes (inaccessible areas or closed groups), but as a variety of social explorations and meanings.

The rituals observed in the Rego da Murta dolmens (figs 2, 3) were similar to those observed in the caves and, although cults here have started at an earlier stage, these spaces continued to be used alongside the constructions and depositions observed further east in the dolmens. Also, the material culture seems to follow the same pattern observed in burial sites all over the Middle Tagus region and therefore can be included in the same social-symbolic system. The GIS analyses of the visibility, slope and appearance combined with the remains observed, some of them absolutely exogenous, either in the caves with the cardinal presence or in the megalithic monuments with the record of external raw materials, allowed us to understand that these structures were closely

related with the society and imposed on landscape an extraordinary openness. It should be noted that dolmens, for instance, are located in areas of easier access. For this case, what was initially considered as a hidden landscape (due to the presence and effective use of caves without a predominant role in landscape marking and that seemed to be somewhat distinct from the patterns and rituals used in neighbouring regions, thus characterizing it as a closed space or at least having typical cultural traditions) is now revealed to be a matter of perception of the archaeological record.

All elements man interacted with were an integral part of a structured landscape which was familiar to the community living in it and incorporated well-known symbolic meanings that superseded material actions (Figueiredo 2006). As our research group proposed since 1985, caves should not be considered as different-meaning elements or as sites having a minor significance in space restructuring. Like megalithic monuments they act as symbolic items for communities, with an active role in the landscape and in the relationship with other people. In the words of Fontijn (2007), ‘invisible places could

Figure 2 – Plan and photographs of dolmen I of Rego da Murta.

have been just as important in ritual landscapes as the visible monuments that we usually study’.

3. The prehistoric art of Ocreza Valley

The prehistoric art of the Ocreza Valley is another example of how the archaeological record interferes with our perception. In the 1970s, during the impact assessment survey for the construction of the Fratel dam, which would eventually submerge the Tagus rupestrian complex, a number of carved panels of relative interest have been identified in the Ocreza valley, a tributary of the Tagus. Further surveys thirty years later enabled us to identify not only more carvings in the Ocreza and another nearby valley (Carvalheiras), but also a number of red paintings (at Pego da Rainha, a spring in the Zimbreira stream, a tributary to the Ocreza). The carved representations on the banks of the Ocreza can be included in two sequences: the upper Palaeolithic, represented by figurative dotted gravures, some of them thread-like, the most important being a headless horse (fig. 4), and a later stage corresponding to recent prehistory (Early Neolithic or Chalcolithic and Early Bronze Age) represented by dotted and thread-like gravures, predominantly schematic, as well as the paintings men-

tioned above which, however, are found in higher, steep areas and sheltered zones (fig. 5).

The artificial lakes resulting from the Pracana and Fratel dams led to the submersion of most rock art panels; only some are uncovered again each summer as the water level decreases. In addition, the difficult access caused by the area’s morphology (steep and abrupt slopes) renders survey of, and comparison between, these remains difficult. An incomplete understanding of the space and distribution of its cultural elements prevents an unequivocal interpretation. The presence of these elements in places of difficult access or even hidden by water hampers the use of common technologies, as for instance, in surveys where underwater archaeology methods have to be used to collect the maximum number of remains and obtain a more complete picture of these actions.

4. Conclusion

Archaeology is concerned to a large extent with reconstructing past landscapes, i.e. perceptions of the territory projected by extinct communities, which is always a challenge. As a matter of fact, hidden landscapes at this level couldn’t exist because a landscape has to be known in order to be considered as such.

Figure 3 – Plan and photographs of dolmen II of Rego da Murta.

However, certain portions of the territory are likely to have been subject to differentiated and probably selected settlements. The fact that, from the Middle Neolithic, burial spaces (in caves or dolmens) tended to be organised in ‘necropolises’ outside the populated areas suggests the construction of a landscape where the land of the dead and the land of the living were dichotomized (in the fashion of Lévi-Strauss). In this context, certain spaces such as burial areas have a double role as hidden landscapes: possibly hidden from some members of those communities in case of limited access (the low, narrow entrances in some monuments suggest that at least their interiors would remain hidden from most community members) and, for sure, hidden from modern communities, who do not recognise them as specific spaces, i.e. who tend not to link them to significant sets of their landscapes/perceptions.

Something similar happens with the rupestrian contexts in Vale do Tejo where a more accessible art engraved at the bottoms of the valleys (what we could call ‘public art’) contrasts with an art painted in exiguous shelters of difficult access. If the former can be hidden from the modern untrained eye, the latter is twice hidden since, due to its difficult access, only a few individuals can enjoy it at a time. In fact, the concept of hidden landscape seems to be more related to the individual who perceives it than to the object that is perceived. Considering a landscape as ‘hidden’ or ‘open’ from the prehistoric point of view is rather complex because we would have to perceive it with the forever lost mental framework of those past communities.

We have nothing to rely on but a number of remains, which more or less conjugated, enable us to draw conclusions on these problems and require supplementary effort in the reconstruction of interpretations and perception of actions. Cult areas such as those containing megalithic art or monuments serve mostly as landmarks of an organized landscape. Even if they were intentionally hidden, they would still be known by society and integrated in the everyday practices of these populations. As we have been suggesting ‘the understanding of a space comprises everything existing therein, always having in mind the set of meanings within it’. From this perspective, the relationship established between man and landscape is always dynamic, intentional and complex. It is dynamic because space functions as a social construction in which man operates benefiting from its own properties or the properties he conferred to it in order to take social,

Figure 4 – Engraving of a headless horse. Palaeolithic, Vale do Ocreza.

Figure 5 – Painting in red of anchor motives. Neolithic, Pego da Rainha.

symbolic or economical advantage of all its constitutive elements. It is intentional because all actions are directed to the organization of that space, even if all elements within it are merely natural, since their meanings may be as important as those pertaining to any artificial architectural structure (Bradley 1998; Fowler & Cummings 2003). It is complex because it is subjective: each individual contribution (Ingold 2000, p. 179) interrelates with others and produces new concepts that shapes the landscape itself: the *Dasein* in Heidegger’s words (Inwood 2000, p. 22; Figueiredo 2006).

Therefore, to consider any of these spaces as a hidden landscape, further tests will be necessary to confirm that this could have been the perspective of those ancestral communities.

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